

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN LIBRARIES

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Paper Received On: 21 August 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 25 September 2024

Published On: 01 October 2024

Abstract

The library will play a very crucial role in the extension and modification of knowledge. The development of knowledge management in recent years has become the key concern for librarian and libraries. Knowledge Management requires more effective methods of information handling, speedy transfer of information. This paper is intended to be an overview to assist knowledge management in terms of its relevance for library and Information science professionals. It also examines the role of librarian/libraries in knowledge Management.

Introduction:-

The concept: Knowledge Management was started and popularized in the business world during the last decade of the 20th Century. It was the business world that first recognize the importance of knowledge in the "global economy" of the "Knowledge age". As a subject discipline of the knowledge economy, knowledge management is completely new concept and method of management. The applications of knowledge management have now spread to other organizations including government agencies, research and development, university and others. Librarian and Information professionals are trained to be experts in information searching, selecting, acquiring, organizing, preserving, repackaging, disseminating and serving. In the 21st century the library will inevitably face the new subject of Knowledge Management.

What is Knowledge Managements: - Knowledge plays an important role in moderm world of organization. Knowledge management is a newly emerging interdisciplinary business model that has knowledge with the frame work of an organization. Knowledge Management involves people, technology and processes in parts. It rests on two foundations first utilizing and exploiting the organization information, second the application of people's skill, talents,

thought, ideas, commitments, motivations and imagination.

Types of Knowledge:-

- **Tacit Knowledge:-** Tacit knowledge is knowledge embedded in human mind through experience and jobs Coined by Hungarian Medial Scientists Michael Polanyi, it include institutions, values and believes that stem from years of experience.
- **Explicit Knowledge:-** In contrast explicit knowledge is knowledge codified and digitized in books, document, reports white paper, spread sheets, training courses and explicit knowledge can be retrieved and transmitted more easily than tacit knowledge. Because it is knowledge learned directly from experience, tacit knowledge is difficult to share across space and time.
- **Externalized Knowledge:** One of the aspects of tacit knowledge is the cognitive dimension that comprises beliefs, ideals, values and mental models.

Need for Knowledge Management:-

- To enhance users satisfaction.
- To interact and retain new information seeker.
- To increase public faith in the organization to strive meet and manage needs of user community.
- To be able to justify the spending of funds allocated to the organization library and information center by the parent body.
- Recruiting the best people for the job.
- Exposing professional to the complexity of real problem to stimulate and cultivate professional's knowhow to retain professionals to react in problem solving techniques.

Components of Knowledge Managements :-

Some essential components of knowledge management are following.

- Treating the knowledge component of business activates as explicit concern of business reflected in strategy. Policy and practice at all levels of the organization.
- Making a direct connection between and organization intellectuals assists both explicit and positive business result.
- Identifying and mapping intellectual assets within the organization generating new knowledge for organization, generating new knowledge for competitive advantage within organization, making vast amounts of corporate information assessable, sharing of best practices and technology enables all of the above.

Knowledge Management in Library Information Centers:-

As a learning organization, libraries should provide a strong leadership in knowledge management. Libraries should improve their knowledge management in all of the key areas of library services. To cope with the exponential growth in human knowledge, libraries need to develop their resources access and sharing strategies from printed to electronic and digital resources. Limited by funding, technology, staff and space, libraries must carefully analyze the need of their users and seek to develop cooperative acquisition plans to meet the needs of users. Libraries should be developed and maintained an integrated online public access catalogue (OPAC) with both internal and external resources as well as printed and other formats of knowledge. Libraries should use the new approach to capture web information by cooperative efforts such as Dublin Core, Metadata and the cooperative online resources catalogue. Other new methods such as data mining text mining, content management, search engines, natural language searching, concept of yellow pages and such technologies in information visualization as two dimensional or three dimensional knowledge mapping.

Information technology & Knowledge Management. :-

To facilitate the implementation of knowledge management, a well-defined and operational knowledge management system should be in place. Latest information technology should be used in the libraries. In this regard, the library director / librarian should consider himself as the chief knowledge officer of the entire organization and should work together with the chief information officer, heads of the planning department, the computer and information technology center, the human resource management department, the finance department etc., to design and develop such a system. Such knowledge management system should be built on the existing computer and information technology infrastructure including upgraded intranet,

Extranet, internet and available software programs to facilitate the capture, analysis, organization, storage and sharing of internal and external information resources for effective knowledge exchange among users.

Information Managers and Knowledge:-

Information managers are professional who act as agents on behalf of information processors to create and continuously improve systems. So that information processors are better able to meet their objectives. Information managers need to be able to understand and interpret these objectives in the context of the resources available to them.

Conclusion:-

Knowledge Management needs to be accepted as a key factor of the overall business strategy.

Library may play an important role in success of knowledge management for their organization. Libraries take care of tacit knowledge in a better way for their successful working and satisfy their customers. Library and information professionals develop appropriate knowledge management system in our organization or libraries. The library and Information professionals are best knowledge creators.

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